

ENDOCRINE DISORDERS IN THE CONTEXT OF COVID-19

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Abstract. *The SARS-CoV-2 virus, which caused the 2019 novel coronavirus disease (COVID-19) pandemic, has presented the healthcare system and the scientific community around the world with an unprecedented challenge. At the time of writing this literature review, the infection has claimed more than 6 million lives, and more than 500 million people worldwide have recovered from SARS-CoV-2. In addition to the main pulmonary manifestations of the disease, as well as severe, life-threatening complications of the acute period of COVID-19, long-term changes that occur in the post-COVID period also affect other systems: endocrine, cardiovascular, nervous and musculoskeletal.*

Keywords: *COVID-19, Thyrotoxicosis, hypercorticism, nuclear thyroidology, thyroid pathology.*

Relevance. There are currently over 480 million confirmed cases of COVID-19 worldwide. The SARS-CoV-2 virus enters human cells primarily through angiotensin-converting enzyme 2 (ACE2) and transmembrane serine protease 2 (TMPRSS2). The spike proteins that coat the coronavirus bind to ACE2 receptors that are present on the surface of human cells. TMPRSS2 facilitates the entry of SARS-CoV-2 into their cytoplasm. The ACE2 receptor is differentially expressed across human organs, with highest expression in the small intestine, followed by the testes, heart, thyroid, kidney, and lung, making these tissues particularly susceptible to these infections. The different ACE2 receptor densities across organs may explain the diversity of symptoms and the spectrum of organ failure seen in COVID-19 patients. Recent observations have shown that SARS-CoV-2 exhibits broad organotropism and can damage endocrine organs in COVID-19 patients. ACE2 and TMPRSS2 are known to be expressed in several endocrine glands: the hypothalamus, pituitary gland, thyroid gland, adrenal glands, gonads, and pancreatic islets, with the highest concentration in the testes, then in the thyroid gland, and the lowest in the hypothalamus.

The purpose of this study. This review provides information on the effects of SARS-CoV-2 infection on thyroid symptoms, the response of thyroid pathology to the disease and the course of COVID-19, and the peculiarities of the behavior of patients with various pathologies of the disease and conditions of new coronavirus infection. It is known that hypothalamic and pituitary tissues express ACE2 and may be potential targets of SARS-CoV-2 either directly or through an immune-mediated process, as has been demonstrated with other coronaviruses [5][6]. Once in the nervous system, SARS-CoV-2 provokes oxidative stress, vasodilation, and thrombogenesis, which together can lead to hemorrhagic pituitary apoplexy.

Materials and methods of research. As mentioned earlier, SARS-CoV-2 uses ACE2 in combination with TMPRSS2 as a key molecular complex to penetrate and infect host cells, and the expression level of ACE2 and TMPRSS2 is quite high in thyroid tissues and higher than in lung tissues. This fact may lead to the sensitivity of the thyroid gland to the SARS-CoV-2 virus. Among the various clinical effects of COVID-19, thyroid damage is considered the most common

endocrine manifestation. It is known that SARS-CoV-2 can affect the entire hypothalamic-pituitary-thyroid axis, thereby causing thyrotoxicosis, hypothyroidism, and non-thyroidal disease syndrome. All cases of central hypothyroidism were transient with restoration of euthyroidism within a year, primary hypothyroidism was permanent, so replacement therapy with sodium levothyroxine was required. The theory of involvement of the hypothalamic-pituitary system is also supported by the identification of the SARS-CoV virus in the hypothalamus during molecular genetic analysis and a decrease in the number of TSH-producing cells of the adenohypophysis according to immunohistochemical studies. In COVID-19, molecular genetic analysis also did not detect SARS-CoV-2 virus RNA in thyroid tissues. However, 64% of patients showed a decrease in the concentration of T3 and/or TSH, which correlated with the severity of COVID-19. These changes are characteristic of euthyroid pathology syndrome, but a third of patients had only a low TSH level, which is not typical for this syndrome. In addition, when comparing comparable patients with severe and extremely severe pneumonia of different etiologies, the degree of suppression of TSH secretion was significantly lower in the SARS-CoV-2 group, which suggests the involvement of other links in the pathogenesis of changes in the thyroid profile - the use of glucocorticosteroids and anticoagulants, direct or mediated by proinflammatory cytokines of the effect of SARS-CoV-2. It is known that SARS-CoV-2 activates the Th1/Th17-cell type of immune response with the release of pro-inflammatory cytokines, primarily IL-6 and TNF, which are responsible for the development of the so-called cytokine "storm". At the same time, high levels of pro-inflammatory IL-6, IL-1 β and TNF are associated with a decrease in the content of T3, T4 and TSH.

Taking into account the possible direct or indirect influence of SARS-CoV-2 through the immune-inflammatory response during the cytokine "storm", a retrospective single-center study THYRCOV assessed thyroid function in patients hospitalized for COVID-19. The study included 287 patients, 5.2% of whom were diagnosed with hypothyroidism (2 cases of overt hypothyroidism and 13 cases of subclinical hypothyroidism), 20.2% - thyrotoxicosis (including 53.4% - overt and 46.6% - subclinical). Moreover, in half of the cases, the course of overt thyrotoxicosis was accompanied by atrial fibrillation or thrombotic complications.

Thyrotoxicosis was associated with high IL-6 levels, longer hospitalization, and the risk of in-hospital mortality. The absence of a typical picture of subacute thyroiditis, the transient nature of thyrotoxicosis, and high IL-6 levels suggest the development of painless destructive thyroiditis mediated by SARS-CoV-2 infection. In another study, the levels of circulating cytokines (IL-6, IL-10, TNF, IFN- γ) did not depend on thyroid function. However, destructive forms of thyrotoxicosis, such as subacute thyroiditis, are most often associated with SARS-CoV-2. Subacute thyroiditis is a transient inflammatory disease of the thyroid gland. The exact causes of this disease remain unknown, but it is assumed that it has a viral etiology, and in most cases, the patient's history indicates a previous viral infection of the upper respiratory tract, influenza, mumps, measles. Destruction of thyroid follicles leads to the release of their contents into the bloodstream, resulting in thyrotoxicosis without hyperfunction of the thyroid gland, followed by the possible formation of transient hypothyroidism, which usually turns into euthyroidism. Other clinical manifestations of subacute thyroiditis include pain in the neck, radiating to the back of the head, ears, lower jaw, increasing with head turns and thyroid palpation. Currently, the question of the possibility of subacute thyroiditis manifestation after a coronavirus infection is particularly relevant. In support of this theory, we will give the following examples. In terms of risks, an

exception is made for patients with an active stage of endocrine ophthalmopathy receiving immunosuppressive therapy, who are classified as a high-risk group for severe COVID-19.

Patients with autoimmune thyroiditis or hypothyroidism receiving replacement therapy with levothyroxine sodium are not considered to be at high risk for severe COVID-19. Given the effect of thyroid hormones on the immune system, it is important to note the importance of replacement therapy with levothyroxine sodium, including in patients hospitalized with COVID-19 in intensive care units. The goal of treatment remains to maintain a stable euthyroid state. It is also advisable for patients receiving suppressive therapy with levothyroxine sodium for operated well-differentiated thyroid cancer (TC) to continue it in the recommended regimen. Patients with cancer are at risk of moderate to severe disease progression and death, which may be due to both the effect of the tumor itself on the immune system and antitumor therapy. In this regard, the issue of tactics for managing patients with thyroid cancer is relevant. Thyroid cancer is the most common malignant neoplasm of the endocrine system, but in most cases, it does not require emergency surgery.

These changes have led to a rapid increase in the relevance of telemedicine in many countries. At the same time, assessing thyroid nodules or the risk of thyroid cancer recurrence is difficult. However, since less than 5% of all thyroid nodules are malignant and no more than 5% of them require emergency surgery, it is considered reasonable to postpone most thyroid surgeries until a more favorable epidemiological situation occurs. The exceptions are high-risk nodules according to the TIRADS system or nodules with clinical signs of compression of surrounding tissues.

Radioiodine therapy I131 is an integral part of the treatment of some thyroid diseases. One of the first challenges facing nuclear thyroidology in 2020 was the prioritization of patients based on the diagnosis with which they seek medical care. At the same time, low doses of I131 are safe and act specifically on thyroid cells that actively absorb this isotope. However, high doses of radioactive iodine, usually used for thyroid cancer with multiple metastases in the lymph nodes, can potentially have an immunosuppressive effect on the red bone marrow, including B-lymphocytes and T-helpers.

A case of pituitary apoplexy (with previously undiagnosed adenoma) associated with COVID-19 in the third trimester of pregnancy is described. Upon admission to the hospital, the patient had been experiencing blurred vision, dilated left pupil, and headache for 4 days; a positive test for SARS-CoV-2 was detected. The patient was prescribed dexamethasone 4 mg 2 times a day, and within 12 hours, the left pupil decreased in size to 4 mm and became more reactive to light, without any other changes during examination. Recent recommendations suggest classifying patients with a positive COVID-19 result who require surgical treatment as urgent or elective, depending on the timing of the surgical intervention. Taking into account the stabilization of symptoms against the background of conservative therapy, the method of choice for treatment was elective surgery after delivery. During transnasal transsphenoidal adenomectomy, identification of the pituitary gland was impossible, a hemorrhagic mass with fibrin was determined. Secondary hypothyroidism and secondary hypogonadism developed 2 months after surgery.

In healthy individuals, glucocorticoids (GC) have an immunostimulating effect in the early phase of the infectious process, increasing the sensitivity of the immune system to external agents. In addition to the known anti-inflammatory and antiallergic effects, there is evidence of increased local innate immune protection in respiratory epithelial cells in response to GC. However, over

time and at consistently high concentrations, the main effects of GC include deep immunosuppression with suppression of the innate and adaptive immune response. Thus, chronic excess of GC prevents the activation of adaptive reactions in patients with hypercorticism. Subsequently, a decrease in the number of B-lymphocytes and T-lymphocytes, as well as the activation of T-helpers, contributes to the development of opportunistic and intracellular infections, and the combination of generalized immunosuppression with impaired immune response leads to chronic sluggish inflammatory processes, which is the cause of a large number of clinical complications. Pre-existing chronic inflammatory diseases are known to increase the risk of COVID-19-related death. In addition to metabolic changes, patients with both endogenous and iatrogenic hypercortisolism have an increased risk of various bacterial, viral, fungal and parasitic infections caused by immunodeficiency.

Endogenous hypercortisolism, i.e., endogenous Cushing's syndrome, is a rare disease with a prevalence of 1.2–2.4 per 100,000 population, while suppressive doses of GCs are received by 1–2% of the population, and iatrogenic hypercortisolism develops in approximately 70% of them. According to the literature, the use of GCs, as well as endogenous excess, can mitigate the hyperimmune reactions responsible for the severe progression of COVID-19. The RECOVERY study found that the administration of dexamethasone 6 mg daily for 10 days is an effective therapy for patients requiring high-flow oxygen or mechanical ventilation, but worsens the prognosis in patients with mild COVID-19. However, the use of exogenous GCs, as well as diseases accompanied by excess endogenous GC production, are often associated with side effects such as obesity, arterial hypertension, cardiovascular diseases, liver steatosis, insulin resistance, and type 2 diabetes mellitus. Interestingly, earlier observations on the use of steroids in Middle East respiratory syndrome (MERS) and SARS gave reason to be skeptical about their use.

Researches and discussion. Even during the SARS epidemic, many patients had low levels of T4 and T3, as well as a decrease in TSH concentration. Moreover, the degree of decrease in thyroid hormone levels depended on the time and severity of the disease; low concentrations of T3 and T4 were found in 94% and 46% of patients with SARS-CoV in the acute phase of infection and in 90% and 38% of convalescents. Reduced T3 levels correlated with the severity of the disease, with minimal values in critically ill patients, which is generally consistent with the euthyroid pathology syndrome, but does not explain the low TSH concentration in a number of patients.

Another study, which included 61 patients with SARS without a history of endocrine pathology 3 months after recovery, identified 4 cases of central hypothyroidism and 1 case of primary hypothyroidism of autoimmune etiology, 39% of patients had signs of secondary hypocorticism, while only a third of the study participants had previously received glucocorticosteroid therapy, in connection with which the authors conclude that hypophysitis develops in patients with SARS-CoV.

The impact of SARS-CoV-2 on the endocrine system has not yet been sufficiently studied. Studies have shown that the virus can affect the gonads, thyroid gland, pituitary gland, adrenal glands and pancreas. There are known cases of manifestation of endocrine pathology after a previous SARS-CoV-2 infection: carbohydrate metabolism disorder, thyroid dysfunction and cases of subacute thyroiditis, adrenal dysfunction, changes in spermatogenesis in men. Given the very short history of COVID-19, it is not yet possible to make final, well-founded conclusions

about the consequences of the disease on the endocrine system; further long-term studies are needed to assess the impact of COVID-19 on the endocrine glands.

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